

Common Best Proximity Point Theorems in Neutrosophic Complete Metric Spaces

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Abstract. In this work, we provide the existence of common best proximity point for a given pair of non-self mappings in non-Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric spaces. Additionally, we prove a corresponding result for non-self mappings in Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric spaces. Our results extend some relevant results of Sasiq Basha [22–24]. Furthermore, we have included examples to support and validate our findings.

Keywords: Best proximity point; Neutrosophic metric; Common best proximity point; Fixed point.

1. Introduction

The idea of indeterminacy, which is crucial for representing uncertainty, ambiguity, and incomplete information, features frequently found in real-world problems, is incorporated into neutrosophic metric spaces, which are an extension of usual metric spaces. Neutrosophic metric spaces are ideal for applications in data analysis, artificial intelligence, and decision-making where information is not always clear or comprehensive because they permit degrees of truth, falsity, and indeterminacy, in contrast to classical metric spaces that depend on exact numerical distances. For the analysis of complex systems, this richer structure offers a more adaptable and practical mathematical framework, particularly in settings where conventional metrics are unable to adequately reflect ambiguity and uncertainty.

As a novel extension of classical set theory, Smarandache [1] created neutrosophic logic and neutrosophic sets. The degree of membership, the degree of indeterminacy, and the degree of non-membership are the three characteristics that define these sets. On top of this, Kiriski et al. developed the idea of neutrosophic metric spaces (NMSs) in [2], and they proved fixed point theorems in complete NMSs in [3]. Motivated by these developments, various researchers

have investigated more general variants of NMSs and applied classical fixed point theorems to this structure; for additional details, see to [4–11]. Notably, Saleem et al. [6] extended fixed point theory to multivalued mappings and applied it to fractal settings, while in [8], Ishtiaq et al. introduced orthogonal NMSs and proved the existence of fixed points within that structure. Recently, Bataihah and Hazaymeh [11] introduced the concept of neutrosophic (L, ϕ) -contractions and established the existence of fixed point for the aforementioned contraction in the setting of neutrosophic metric spaces.

On the other hand, best proximity point theory plays a significant role in nonlinear analysis and optimization by offering solutions in cases where fixed points do not exist. One frequently comes across mappings between two disjoint sets in real-world applications in disciplines like computer science, engineering, and economics where a point cannot be mapped to itself. In these situations, the best proximity point theory minimizes the distance between two sets by identifying points in one set that are closest to their corresponding pictures in the other. This method goes beyond traditional fixed point theory and is crucial for solving variational inequalities, equilibrium models, and limited optimization problems where exact solutions are not achievable but the closest approximations are pertinent and helpful.

Suppose M_1, M_2 be two non-empty subsets of a metric space (Ω, d) and $\Gamma_1 : M_1 \rightarrow M_2$. Then Γ is said to have a best proximity point in M_1 if we can find an element $x \in M_1$ such that

$$d(x, \Gamma x) = d(M_1, M_2) = \inf\{d(a, b) : a \in M_1 \text{ and } b \in M_2\}.$$

Here, note that, when $M_1 = M_2$, the best proximity point is nothing but a fixed point.

Best proximity point theorems are studied to find the necessary conditions under which the minimization problem $\min_{x \in M_1} d(x, \Gamma x)$ has at least one solution. The existence and convergence of best proximity points is an interesting topic in optimization theory, which has recently attracted the attention of many authors [12–17]. A best proximity point theorem for non-self proximal contractions is investigated in [18–21]. Suppose we have another mapping $\Gamma_2 : M_1 \rightarrow M_2$. Then the mappings Γ_1 and Γ_2 is said to have a common best proximity point in M_1 if we can find an element $x \in M_1$ such that

$$d(x, \Gamma_1 x) = d(M_1, M_2) = d(x, \Gamma_2 x).$$

Here, when $M_1 = M_2$, the common best proximity point is a common fixed point.

Sadiq Basha et al. [22] have investigated a common best proximity theorem for mappings that satisfy a contraction-like condition. A common best proximity point theorem for pairs of contractive non-self mappings and for pairs of contraction non-self mappings has been explored in [23]. Sadiq Basha [24] has investigated a common best proximity point theorem for proximally commuting non-self mappings, an improved approach to which has been discussed

in [25]. For detailed analysis on common best proximity point for several types of contractions in different spaces, we direct the reader to see [26–36] and references therein.

The existence of common best proximity points for non-self mappings within neutrosophic complete metric spaces has, to date, not been studied. In this work, we bridge this gap by establishing the existence of the common best proximity points for non-self mappings.

The paper is arranged as follows. We begin by introducing the notions like neutrosophic proximally commutativity, proximal neutrosophic domination of a mapping, and neutrosophic proximal interchangeability to the framework of neutrosophic metric spaces. Later, we establish sufficient conditions under which a non-self mapping ensures the existence of the common best proximity points for a non-self map. In addition, we provide examples to support our results.

2. Preliminaries:

Definition 2.1. [37] An operation $*$: $[0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a continuous t-norm (CTN) if $*$ satisfies conditions below:

- (I) $a * 1 = a$,
- (II) $*$ is commutative and associative
- (III) $*$ is continuous
- (IV) $a * b \leq u * v$ whenever $a \leq u$, $b \leq v$, and $a, b, u, v \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.2. [37] An operation \diamond : $[0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a continuous t-conorm (CTCN) if \diamond satisfies conditions below:

- (I) $a \diamond 0 = a$
- (II) \diamond is commutative and associative
- (III) \diamond is continuous
- (IV) $a \diamond b \leq u \diamond v$ whenever $a \leq u$ and $b \leq v$, and $a, b, u, v \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.3. [38] Assume R is a non-empty set. Consider a six-tuple $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$, where $*$ signifies a continuous t-norm (CTN), \diamond denotes a continuous t-conorm (CTCN), and P_ϕ, E_ϕ, Z_ϕ are neutrosophic sets defined on $R \times R \times (0, \infty)$. If this six-tuple satisfies the subsequent conditions for all $\xi, \nu, r \in R$ and for all positive scalars τ_1, τ_2 :

- (I) $P_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) + E_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) + Z_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) \leq 3$
- (II) $0 \leq P_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) \leq 1$
- (III) $P_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = 1 \iff \xi = \nu$
- (IV) $P_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = P_\phi(\nu, \xi, \tau_1)$
- (V) $P_\phi(\xi, r, \tau_1 + \tau_2) \geq P_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) * P_\phi(\nu, r, \tau_2)$
- (VI) The function $P_\phi(\xi, \nu, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous

- (VII) $\lim_{\tau_1 \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = 1$
 (VIII) $0 \leq E_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) \leq 1$
 (IX) $E_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = 0 \iff \xi = \nu$
 (X) $E_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = E_\phi(\nu, \xi, \tau_1)$
 (XI) $E_\phi(\xi, r, \tau_1 + \tau_2) \leq E_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) \diamond E_\phi(\nu, r, \tau_2)$
 (XII) The function $E_\phi(\xi, \nu, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous
 (XIII) $\lim_{\tau_1 \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = 0$
 (XIV) $0 \leq Z_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) \leq 1$
 (XV) $Z_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = 0 \iff \xi = \nu$
 (XVI) $Z_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = Z_\phi(\nu, \xi, \tau_1)$
 (XVII) $Z_\phi(\xi, r, \tau_1 + \tau_2) \leq Z_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) \diamond Z_\phi(\nu, r, \tau_2)$
 (XVIII) The function $Z_\phi(\xi, \nu, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous
 (XIX) $\lim_{\tau_1 \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = 0$
 (XX) For $\tau_1 \leq 0$, we have $P_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = 0$, $E_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = 1$, and $Z_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau_1) = 1$.

Then, (P_ϕ, E_ϕ, Z_ϕ) is termed a *neutrosophic metric* on R , and $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ is designated a **neutrosophic metric space (NMS)**. The functions P_ϕ , E_ϕ , and Z_ϕ articulate the degrees of membership for nearness, indeterminacy, and non-nearness, respectively.

- (XXI) $P_\phi(\xi, r, \tau) \geq P_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau) * P_\phi(\nu, r, \tau)$
 (XXII) $E_\phi(\xi, r, \tau) \leq E_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(\nu, r, \tau)$
 (XXIII) $Z_\phi(\xi, r, \tau) \leq Z_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(\nu, r, \tau)$.

Furthermore, if conditions (V), (XI), and (XVII) are substituted by (XXI), (XXII), and (XXIII) respectively, then $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ is referred to as a **non-Archimedean neutrosophic metric space (non-Archimedean NMS)**.

Example 2.4. [38] Consider a metric space (R, Ω) . The following functions are defined: $P_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) = \frac{\tau}{\tau + \Omega(\omega_1, \omega_2)}$, $E_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) = \frac{\Omega(\omega_1, \omega_2)}{\tau + \Omega(\omega_1, \omega_2)}$, and $Z_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) = \frac{\Omega(\omega_1, \omega_2)}{\tau}$, for all $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in R$ and $\tau > 0$. In this scenario, $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ is known as the *standard NMS* induced by the metric Ω .

Definition 2.5. [38] Let $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ be a neutrosophic metric space (NMS). An open ball centered at $\omega_1 \in R$, with radius $0 < r < 1$, and parameter $\tau > 0$ is specified as:

$$B(\omega_1, r, \tau) = \{\omega_2 \in R : P_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) > 1 - r, E_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) < r, Z_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) < r\}.$$

The topology on R induced by the neutrosophic metric is given by:

$$\tau(P_\phi, E_\phi) = \{A \subset R : \forall \omega_1 \in A, \exists \tau > 0, r \in (0, 1) \text{ such that } B(\omega_1, r, \tau) \subset A\}.$$

This $\tau(P_\phi, E_\phi)$ is then designated as the topology on R arising from the neutrosophic metric.

Definition 2.6. [38] Let $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ represent a neutrosophic metric space (NMS).

- A sequence $\{\zeta_n\}$ in R is deemed to converge to a point $\zeta \in R$ if, for every $\tau > 0$, the following limits hold: $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(\zeta_n, \zeta, \tau) = 1$; $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(\zeta_n, \zeta, \tau) = 0$; $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(\zeta_n, \zeta, \tau) = 0$.
- A sequence $\{\zeta_n\}$ in R is declared to be a Cauchy sequence if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $\tau > 0$, there exists a natural number $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n, m \geq n_0$, we have: $P_\phi(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \tau) > 1 - \epsilon$; $E_\phi(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \tau) < \epsilon$; $Z_\phi(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \tau) < \epsilon$.
- The space is considered complete if every Cauchy sequence within R converges to a point in R .
- The space is considered compact if every sequence $\{\zeta_n\}$ in R admits a convergent subsequence $\{\zeta_{n_k}\}$.

The concept of a best proximity point for non-self mappings is articulated as follows.

Definition 2.7. Let (C, D) be a pair of non-empty subsets of a neutrosophic metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$. An element $\zeta \in C$ is defined as a best proximity point for the non-self map $\Gamma : C \rightarrow D$ if it fulfills the conditions: $P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma\zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma\zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma\zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$ for all $\tau > 0$.

Remark 2.8. In Definition 2.7, when the sets C and D are identical ($C = D$), the conditions simplify to: $P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma\zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 1$, $E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma\zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 0$, and $Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma\zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 0$ for all $\tau > 0$. This implies that $\zeta = \Gamma\zeta$, which indicates that ζ is a fixed point for the self-map Γ .

Definition 2.9. Let (C, D) represent two non-empty subsets of a neutrosophic metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$. An element $\zeta \in C$ is termed a common best proximity point for two non-self mappings $\Gamma_1 : C \rightarrow D$ and $\Gamma_2 : C \rightarrow D$ if it concurrently satisfies the following criteria: $P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$ for all $\tau > 0$.

Remark 2.10. It is noteworthy that in Definition 2.9, if the sets C and D are identical (i.e., $C = D$), the stipulated conditions simplify considerably to: $P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 1$, $E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 0$, and $Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 0$ for all $\tau > 0$. These simplifications directly imply that $\zeta = \Gamma_1\zeta$ and $\zeta = \Gamma_2\zeta$. Consequently, ζ serves as a common fixed point for the self-maps Γ_1 and Γ_2 .

Given non-empty subsets C and D of a neutrosophic metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$, the subsequent definitions are employed:

$$P_\phi(C, D, \tau) := \sup\{P_\phi(\zeta, \nu, \tau) : \zeta \in C \text{ and } \nu \in D\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_\phi(C, D, \tau) &:= \inf\{E_\phi(\zeta, \nu, \tau) : \zeta \in C \text{ and } \nu \in D\} \\
 Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) &:= \inf\{Z_\phi(\zeta, \nu, \tau) : \zeta \in C \text{ and } \nu \in D\} \\
 C_0(\tau) &= \left\{ \zeta \in C \left| \begin{array}{l} P_\phi(\zeta, \nu, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), E_\phi(\zeta, \nu, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \text{ and} \\ Z_\phi(\zeta, \nu, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \text{ for some } \nu \in D \end{array} \right. \right\} \\
 D_0(\tau) &= \left\{ \nu \in D \left| \begin{array}{l} P_\phi(\zeta, \nu, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), E_\phi(\zeta, \nu, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \text{ and} \\ Z_\phi(\zeta, \nu, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \text{ for some } \zeta \in C \end{array} \right. \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

for all $\tau > 0$.

Definition 2.11. If every sequence $\{\delta_n\}$ in D that fulfills the condition that $P_\phi(\varsigma, \delta_n, \tau) \rightarrow P_\phi(\varsigma, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(\varsigma, \delta_n, \tau) \rightarrow E_\phi(\varsigma, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(\varsigma, \delta_n, \tau) \rightarrow Z_\phi(\varsigma, D, \tau)$, for some ς in C and for all $\tau > 0$ possesses a convergent subsequence, then the set D is deemed to be approximately compact with respect to C .

Next, we define the concepts of neutrosophic proximal commutativity, proximal neutrosophic domination of a mapping, and neutrosophic proximal interchangeability in order to establish our main results.

Definition 2.12. The mappings $\Gamma_2 : C \rightarrow D$ and $\Gamma_1 : C \rightarrow D$ are said to neutrosophic proximally commute if:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} P_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(\nu, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(\nu, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(\nu, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{array} \right\} \implies \Gamma_2\nu = \Gamma_1\xi$$

for all ξ, ζ, ν in C and $\tau > 0$.

Definition 2.13. A mapping $\Gamma_1 : C \rightarrow D$ is said to proximally neutrosophic dominate a mapping $\Gamma_2 : C \rightarrow D$ if there exists a non-negative real number $k \in [0, 1)$ such that, for all $\xi_1, \xi_2, \nu_1, \nu_2, \zeta_1, \zeta_2$ in C , the following implications hold:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} P_\phi(\xi_1, \Gamma_2\zeta_1, \tau) = P_\phi(\xi_2, \Gamma_2\zeta_2, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ P_\phi(\nu_1, \Gamma_1\zeta_1, \tau) = P_\phi(\nu_2, \Gamma_1\zeta_2, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{array} \right\} \implies P_\phi(\xi_1, \xi_2, k\tau) \geq P_\phi(\nu_1, \nu_2, \tau)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} E_\phi(\xi_1, \Gamma_2\zeta_1, \tau) = E_\phi(\xi_2, \Gamma_2\zeta_2, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\nu_1, \Gamma_1\zeta_1, \tau) = E_\phi(\nu_2, \Gamma_1\zeta_2, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{array} \right\} \implies E_\phi(\xi_1, \xi_2, k\tau) \leq E_\phi(\nu_1, \nu_2, \tau)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} Z_\phi(\xi_1, \Gamma_2\zeta_1, \tau) = Z_\phi(\xi_2, \Gamma_2\zeta_2, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\nu_1, \Gamma_1\zeta_1, \tau) = Z_\phi(\nu_2, \Gamma_1\zeta_2, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{array} \right\} \implies Z_\phi(\xi_1, \xi_2, k\tau) \leq Z_\phi(\nu_1, \nu_2, \tau)$$

for all $\tau > 0$.

Definition 2.14. It is asserted that the mappings $\Gamma_2 : C \rightarrow D$ and $\Gamma_1 : C \rightarrow D$ can be neutrosophic proximally interchanged if:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\varsigma, \xi, \tau) &= P_\phi(\varsigma, \nu, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\varsigma, \xi, \tau) &= E_\phi(\varsigma, \nu, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\varsigma, \xi, \tau) &= Z_\phi(\varsigma, \nu, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ \Gamma_2\xi &= \Gamma_1\nu \end{aligned} \right\} \implies \Gamma_2\nu = \Gamma_1\xi$$

for all ξ, ν in C , $\varsigma \in D$ and $\tau > 0$.

3. Main Results:

Theorem 3.1. Let (C, D) be a pair of non-empty closed subsets of a non-Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ such that $C_0(\tau)$ is non-empty and C is approximately compact with respect to D . Additionally, assume $\Gamma_1 : C \rightarrow D$ and $\Gamma_2 : C \rightarrow D$ are non-self mappings satisfying the following conditions:

- (a) There exists a non-negative real number $k \leq 1$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_1, \Gamma_2\zeta_2, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_1, \Gamma_1\zeta_2, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_1, \Gamma_2\zeta_2, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_1, \Gamma_1\zeta_2, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_1, \Gamma_2\zeta_2, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_1, \Gamma_1\zeta_2, \tau) \end{aligned}$$

for all ζ_1 and ζ_2 in C .

- (b) Γ_1 is continuous.
- (c) Γ_2 and Γ_1 neutrosophic proximally commute.
- (d) Γ_2 and Γ_1 can be neutrosophic proximally interchanged.
- (e) $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq D_0(\tau)$ and $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq \Gamma_1(C_0(\tau))$.

Then, there exists an element $\zeta \in C$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) &= P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) &= E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) &= Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{aligned}$$

That is, ζ constitutes a common best proximity point for Γ_1 and Γ_2 .

Proof

Let ζ_0 be an element in $C_0(\tau)$. Given that $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq \Gamma_1(C_0(\tau))$, there exists an element ζ_1 in $C_0(\tau)$ such that $\Gamma_2\zeta_0 = \Gamma_1\zeta_1$. Continuing this process inductively, we establish the existence of a sequence $\{\zeta_n\}$ in $C_0(\tau)$ such that $\Gamma_2\zeta_n = \Gamma_1\zeta_{n+1}$, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

From condition (a), it follows that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_n, \Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_n, \Gamma_1\zeta_{n+1}, \tau) = P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n-1}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_n, \Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_n, \Gamma_1\zeta_{n+1}, \tau) = E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n-1}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_n, \Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_n, \Gamma_1\zeta_{n+1}, \tau) = Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n-1}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ and } k \in (0, 1). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

By employing mathematical induction, we derive

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_1, \Gamma_2\zeta_0, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_1, \Gamma_2\zeta_0, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_1, \Gamma_2\zeta_0, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ and } k \in (0, 1). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

Hence, for any positive integer q , we obtain

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_n, \Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, \tau) * \dots * (\text{q-times}) \dots * P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q-1}, \Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q}, \tau) \\ &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_0, \Gamma_2\zeta_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}) * \dots * (\text{q-times}) \dots * P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_0, \Gamma_2\zeta_1, \frac{\tau}{k^{n+q-1}}), \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_n, \Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond \dots * (\text{q-times}) \dots \diamond E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q-1}, \Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q}, \tau) \\ &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_0, \Gamma_2\zeta_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}) \diamond \dots * (\text{q-times}) \dots \diamond E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_0, \Gamma_2\zeta_1, \frac{\tau}{k^{n+q-1}}), \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_n, \Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond \dots * (\text{q-times}) \dots \diamond Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q-1}, \Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q}, \tau) \\ &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_0, \Gamma_2\zeta_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}) \diamond \dots * (\text{q-times}) \dots \diamond Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_0, \Gamma_2\zeta_1, \frac{\tau}{k^{n+q-1}}). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

Now, from (3) and the properties of a neutrosophic metric space (NMS), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau) &\geq 1 * \dots * (\text{q-times}) \dots * 1 = 1, \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau) &\leq 0 \diamond \dots * (\text{q-times}) \dots \diamond 0 = 0, \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+q}, \Gamma_2\zeta_n, \tau) &\leq 0 \diamond \dots * (\text{q-times}) \dots \diamond 0 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

It is thus established that $\{\Gamma_2\zeta_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence, which consequently converges to some point ξ in D . As a result, the sequence $\{\Gamma_1\zeta_n\}$ also converges to ξ . Considering that $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq D_0(\tau)$, there exists an element ξ_n in C such that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_n, \xi_n, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_n, \xi_n, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_n, \xi_n, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \quad \text{for every } n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, it follows from the construction of ζ_n that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_n, \xi_{n-1}, \tau) &= P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n-1}, \xi_{n-1}, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_n, \xi_{n-1}, \tau) &= E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n-1}, \xi_{n-1}, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_n, \xi_{n-1}, \tau) &= Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n-1}, \xi_{n-1}, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Since Γ_2 and Γ_1 are neutrosophic proximally commuting, from (4) and (5), we deduce

$$\Gamma_1 \xi_n = \Gamma_2 \xi_{n-1}, \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Furthermore, we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\xi, C, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(\xi, \xi_n, \tau) \\ &\geq P_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \tau) * P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \xi_n, \tau) \\ &= P_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \tau) * P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ &\geq P_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \tau) * P_\phi(\xi, C, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Also,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E_\phi(\xi, C, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(\xi, \xi_n, \tau) \\ &\leq E_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \xi_n, \tau) \\ &= E_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ &\leq E_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(\xi, C, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Similarly,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Z_\phi(\xi, C, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\xi, \xi_n, \tau) \\ &\leq Z_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \xi_n, \tau) \\ &= Z_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ &\leq Z_\phi(\xi, \Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(\xi, C, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8)$$

From (6), (7), and (8), we infer $P_\phi(\xi, \xi_n, \tau) \rightarrow P_\phi(\xi, C, \tau)$, $E_\phi(\xi, \xi_n, \tau) \rightarrow E_\phi(\xi, C, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(\xi, \xi_n, \tau) \rightarrow Z_\phi(\xi, C, \tau)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Since C is approximatively compact with respect to D , the sequence $\{\xi_n\}$ possesses a convergent subsequence $\{\xi_{n_k}\}$ converging to some $\xi^* \in C$. Furthermore, given that $P_\phi(\xi, \xi_{n_k}, \tau) \rightarrow P_\phi(\xi, C, \tau)$, $E_\phi(\xi, \xi_{n_k}, \tau) \rightarrow E_\phi(\xi, C, \tau)$ and $Z_\phi(\xi, \xi_{n_k}, \tau) \rightarrow Z_\phi(\xi, C, \tau)$, and C is approximately compact with respect to D , the sequence $\{\xi_{n_k}\}$ has a subsequence $\{\xi_{n_{k_j}}\}$ converging to some element ν in C .

Due to the continuity of the mappings Γ_2 and Γ_1 ,

$$\Gamma_1 \xi^* = \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \Gamma_1 \xi_{n_{k_j}} = \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \Gamma_2 \xi_{n_{k_j} - 1} = \Gamma_2 \xi^*. \quad (9)$$

Moreover,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\xi, \xi^*, \tau) &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \zeta_{n_k}, \xi_{n_k}, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ P_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau) &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(\Gamma_1 \xi_{n_{k_j}}, \xi_{n_{k_j-1}}, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\xi, \xi^*, \tau) &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \zeta_{n_k}, \xi_{n_k}, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau) &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(\Gamma_1 \xi_{n_{k_j}}, \xi_{n_{k_j-1}}, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\xi, \xi^*, \tau) &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \zeta_{n_k}, \xi_{n_k}, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\xi, \nu, \tau) &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(\Gamma_1 \xi_{n_{k_j}}, \xi_{n_{k_j-1}}, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Since Γ_2 and Γ_1 can be neutrosophic proximally interchanged, from (9), and (10), we ascertain $\Gamma_1 \nu = \Gamma_2 \xi^*$.

Ultimately, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma_1 \xi^*, \Gamma_1 \nu, \tau) = P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma_1 \xi^*, \Gamma_1 \nu, \tau) = E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_1 \xi^*, \Gamma_1 \nu, \tau) = Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \tau), \end{aligned}$$

Now, from the preceding relations, we derive

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \tau) \geq P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \frac{\tau}{k}) \geq P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \frac{\tau}{k^2}) \\ &\geq \dots \geq P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \frac{\tau}{k^n}) \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \\ 0 &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \tau) \leq E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \frac{\tau}{k}) \leq E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \frac{\tau}{k^2}) \\ &\leq \dots \leq E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \frac{\tau}{k^n}) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \\ 0 &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \tau) \leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \frac{\tau}{k}) \leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \frac{\tau}{k^2}) \\ &\leq \dots \leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \nu, \frac{\tau}{k^n}) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \end{aligned}$$

which signifies that $\Gamma_2 \xi^* = \Gamma_2 \nu$ and, in turn, $\Gamma_1 \xi^* = \Gamma_2 \xi^*$.

Since $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau))$ is a subset of $D_0(\tau)$, there exists an element $\zeta \in C$ that satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1 \xi^*, \tau) &= P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2 \xi^*, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1 \xi^*, \tau) &= E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2 \xi^*, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1 \xi^*, \tau) &= Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2 \xi^*, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \end{aligned}$$

and since Γ_2 and Γ_1 are neutrosophic proximally commuting, $\Gamma_2 \zeta = \Gamma_1 \zeta$.

Consequently, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \zeta, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma_1 \xi^*, \Gamma_1 \zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \zeta, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \zeta, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma_1 \xi^*, \Gamma_1 \zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \zeta, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \zeta, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_1 \xi^*, \Gamma_1 \zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \xi^*, \Gamma_2 \zeta, \tau), \end{aligned}$$

which mandates that $\Gamma_2\xi^* = \Gamma_2\zeta$ and therefore $\Gamma_1\xi^* = \Gamma_1\zeta$. Thus, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) &= P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) &= E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1\zeta, \tau) &= Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2\zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, ζ is a common best proximity point for the mappings Γ_2 and Γ_1 .

This completes the proof of the theorem.

Example 3.2. Consider \mathbb{R}^2 with metric $d((x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2)) = |x_1 - x_2| + |y_1 - y_2|$. Choose $C = \{(x, y) \mid x \leq -1, y \in \mathbb{R}\}$ and $D = \{(x, y) \mid x \geq 1, y \in \mathbb{R}\}$. Here, $C_0(\tau) = \{(-1, y) \mid y \in \mathbb{R}\}$ and $D_0(\tau) = \{(1, y) \mid y \in \mathbb{R}\}$. Define $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 : C \rightarrow D$ as $\Gamma_1(x, y) = (-x, \frac{y}{4})$ and $\Gamma_2(x, y) = (-x, \frac{y}{5})$. Choose the CTN, $*$ as $a * b = ab$ and the CCTN \diamond as $a \diamond b = \max\{a, b\}$. The functions $P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi : \mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2 \times [0, \infty)$ are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(z_i, z_{i+1}, \tau) &= \frac{1}{1 + d(z_i, z_{i+1})}, \\ E_\phi(z_i, z_{i+1}, \tau) &= \frac{d(z_i, z_{i+1})}{1 + d(z_i, z_{i+1})}, \\ Z_\phi(z_i, z_{i+1}, \tau) &= d(z_i, z_{i+1}), \end{aligned}$$

where $z_i = (x_i, y_i)$ and $z_{i+1} = (x_{i+1}, y_{i+1})$, for $x_i, y_i, x_{i+1}, y_{i+1} \in \mathbb{R}$. And we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(C, D, \tau) &= \frac{1}{3}, \\ E_\phi(C, D, \tau) &= \frac{2}{3}, \\ Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) &= 2, \tau > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Claim I: There exists a non-negative real number $k \leq 1$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2z_1, \Gamma_2z_2, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma_1z_1, \Gamma_1z_2, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_2z_1, \Gamma_2z_2, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma_1z_1, \Gamma_1z_2, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_2z_1, \Gamma_2z_2, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_1z_1, \Gamma_1z_2, \tau), \end{aligned}$$

for all $z_1 = (x_1, y_1)$ and $z_2 = (x_2, y_2)$ in C .

Subclaim 1: $P_\phi(\Gamma_2z_1, \Gamma_2z_2, k\tau) \geq P_\phi(\Gamma_1z_1, \Gamma_1z_2, \tau)$.

Consider

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2(x_1, y_1), \Gamma_2(x_2, y_2), k\tau) &= P_\phi\left(\left(-x_1, \frac{y_1}{5}\right), \left(-x_2, \frac{y_2}{5}\right), k\tau\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + |x_1 - x_2| + \left|\frac{y_1}{5} - \frac{y_2}{5}\right|} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{1 + |x_1 - x_2| + \left|\frac{y_1}{4} - \frac{y_2}{4}\right|} \\ &= P_\phi(\Gamma_1(x_1, y_1), \Gamma_1(x_2, y_2), \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Subclaim 2: $E_\phi(\Gamma_2 z_1, \Gamma_2 z_2, k\tau) \leq E_\phi(\Gamma_1 z_1, \Gamma_1 z_2, \tau)$.

Consider

$$\begin{aligned} E_\phi(\Gamma_2(x_1, y_1), \Gamma_2(x_2, y_2), k\tau) &= E_\phi\left(\left(-x_1, \frac{y_1}{5}\right), \left(-x_2, \frac{y_2}{5}\right), k\tau\right) \\ &= \frac{|x_1 - x_2| + \left|\frac{y_1}{5} - \frac{y_2}{5}\right|}{1 + |x_1 - x_2| + \left|\frac{y_1}{5} - \frac{y_2}{5}\right|} \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{|x_1 - x_2| + \left|\frac{y_1}{5} - \frac{y_2}{5}\right|}} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{|x_1 - x_2| + \left|\frac{y_1}{4} - \frac{y_2}{4}\right|}} \\ &= E_\phi(\Gamma_1(x_1, y_1), \Gamma_1(x_2, y_2), \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Subclaim 3: $Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 z_1, \Gamma_2 z_2, k\tau) \leq Z_\phi(\Gamma_1 z_1, \Gamma_1 z_2, \tau)$.

Consider

$$\begin{aligned} Z_\phi(\Gamma_2(x_1, y_1), \Gamma_2(x_2, y_2), k\tau) &= Z_\phi\left(\left(-x_1, \frac{y_1}{5}\right), \left(-x_2, \frac{y_2}{5}\right), k\tau\right) \\ &= |x_1 - x_2| + \left|\frac{y_1}{5} - \frac{y_2}{5}\right| \\ &\leq |x_1 - x_2| + \left|\frac{y_1}{4} - \frac{y_2}{4}\right| \\ &= Z_\phi(\Gamma_1(x_1, y_1), \Gamma_1(x_2, y_2), \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Hence it holds for any $k \in [0, 1)$. Thus Γ_1 and Γ_2 satisfies the contraction condition.

Claim II: Γ_2 and Γ_1 neutrosophic proximally commute.

Let $w_1, w_2, z \in C$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(w_1, \Gamma_2 z, \tau) &= P_\phi(w_2, \Gamma_1 z, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(w_1, \Gamma_2 z, \tau) &= E_\phi(w_2, \Gamma_1 z, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(w_1, \Gamma_2 z, \tau) &= Z_\phi(w_2, \Gamma_1 z, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Then the only possible values of z, w_1 , and w_2 are given by $z = (-1, y), w_1 = (-1, \frac{y}{5})$, and $w_2 = (-1, \frac{y}{4})$, for any $y \in \mathbb{R}$. Thus $\Gamma_1 w_1 = \Gamma_2 w_2 = (1, \frac{y}{20})$. Hence Γ_2 and Γ_1 neutrosophic proximally commute.

Claim III: Γ_2 and Γ_1 can be neutrosophic proximally interchanged.

Let $w_1, w_2 \in C$ and $z \in D$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(w_1, z, \tau) &= P_\phi(w_2, z, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(w_1, z, \tau) &= E_\phi(w_2, z, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(w_1, z, \tau) &= Z_\phi(w_2, z, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \end{aligned}$$

and $\Gamma_2 w_1 = \Gamma_1 w_2$.

Then the only possible values of z, w_1 and w_2 are given by $z = (1, y)$, we have $w_1 = (-1, y) = w_2$ for any $y \in \mathbb{R}$. Note that $\Gamma_2 w_1 = (1, \frac{y}{5}) = \Gamma_1 w_2 = (1, \frac{y}{4})$. Thus $y = 0$ and we obtain $z = (1, 0)$. Now we get $\Gamma_2 w_2 = \Gamma_1 w_1$ which implies that Γ_2 and Γ_1 can be neutrosophic proximally interchanged.

Clearly, $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq D_0(\tau)$ and $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq \Gamma_1(C_0(\tau))$ and the function Γ_1 is continuous. Thus, by Theorem 3.1, Γ the mappings Γ_1 and Γ_2 has a common best proximity point $(-1, 0)$ in C .

Theorem 3.3. *Let (C, D) be a pair of non-empty closed subsets of an Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ such that $C_0(\tau)$ is non-empty and closed. Also, assume $\Gamma_1 : C \rightarrow D$ and $\Gamma_2 : C \rightarrow D$ are non-self mappings satisfying the following conditions:*

- (a) Γ_1 proximally neutrosophic dominates Γ_2 .
- (b) Γ_2 and Γ_1 are continuous.
- (c) Γ_2 and Γ_1 are neutrosophic proximally commuting.
- (d) $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq D_0(\tau)$ and $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq \Gamma_1(C_0(\tau))$.

Then, there exists a unique element $\zeta \in C$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1 \zeta, \tau) &= P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2 \zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1 \zeta, \tau) &= E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2 \zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1 \zeta, \tau) &= Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2 \zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{aligned}$$

That is, ζ is a unique common best proximity point for Γ_1 and Γ_2 .

Proof. Following the proof of Theorem 3.1, a sequence $\{\zeta_n\}$ exists in $C_0(\tau)$ such that $\Gamma_2 \zeta_n = \Gamma_1 \zeta_{n+1}$, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Now, since $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq D_0(\tau)$, there exists ξ_n in $C_0(\tau)$ such that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \xi_n, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \xi_n, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_2 \zeta_n, \xi_n, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{11}$$

Furthermore, based on the selection of ζ_n and ξ_n , it is established that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, \xi_{n+1}, \tau) &= P_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_n, \xi_{n-1}, \tau) = P_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_{n+1}, \xi_n, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, \xi_{n+1}, \tau) &= E_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_n, \xi_{n-1}, \tau) = E_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_{n+1}, \xi_n, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma_2\zeta_{n+1}, \xi_{n+1}, \tau) &= Z_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_n, \xi_{n-1}, \tau) = Z_\phi(\Gamma_1\zeta_{n+1}, \xi_n, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{12}$$

Since Γ_1 proximally neutrosophic dominates Γ_2 , from 11 and 12, we obtain

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\xi_{n+1}, \xi_n, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(\xi_n, \xi_{n-1}, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\xi_{n+1}, \xi_n, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(\xi_n, \xi_{n-1}, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\xi_{n+1}, \xi_n, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\xi_n, \xi_{n-1}, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{13}$$

By mathematical induction, we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\xi_{n+1}, \xi_n, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(\xi_0, \xi_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \\ E_\phi(\xi_{n+1}, \xi_n, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(\xi_0, \xi_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \\ Z_\phi(\xi_{n+1}, \xi_n, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\xi_0, \xi_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ and } k \in (0, 1). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{14}$$

Thus, for any positive integer q , we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\xi_{n+q}, \xi_n, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(\xi_n, \xi_{n+1}, \frac{\tau}{q}) * \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots * P_\phi(\xi_{n+q-1}, \xi_{n+q}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \\ &\geq P_\phi(\xi_0, \xi_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^n}) * \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots * P_\phi(\xi_0, \xi_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^{n+q-1}}), \\ E_\phi(\xi_{n+q}, \xi_n, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(\xi_n, \xi_{n+1}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond E_\phi(\xi_{n+q-1}, \xi_{n+q}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \\ &\leq E_\phi(\xi_0, \xi_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^n}) \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond E_\phi(\xi_0, \xi_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^{n+q-1}}), \\ Z_\phi(\xi_{n+q}, \xi_n, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\xi_n, \xi_{n+1}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond Z_\phi(\xi_{n+q-1}, \xi_{n+q}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \\ &\leq Z_\phi(\xi_0, \xi_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^n}) \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond Z_\phi(\xi_0, \xi_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^{n+q-1}}). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{15}$$

Now, by (15) and the definition of NMS conditions, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(\xi_{n+q}, \xi_n, \tau) &\geq 1 * \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots * 1 = 1, \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(\xi_{n+q}, \xi_n, \tau) &\leq 0 \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond 0 = 0, \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(\xi_{n+q}, \xi_n, \tau) &\leq 0 \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond 0 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\{\xi_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in $C_0(\tau)$ and consequently converges to some element $\xi^* \in C_0(\tau)$. Since the mappings Γ_2 and Γ_1 are neutrosophic proximally commuting, from 12, we get $\Gamma_1\xi_n = \Gamma_2\xi_{n-1}$, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Therefore, the continuity of the mappings Γ_2 and Γ_1 guarantees that $\Gamma_2\xi^*$ and $\Gamma_1\xi^*$ are identical, and $\Gamma_2\xi^* = \Gamma_1\xi^* \in \Gamma_2(C_0(\tau))$. Since $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq$

$D_0(\tau)$, there exists an element $\zeta \in C_0(\tau)$ such that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1 \xi^*, \tau) &= P_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2 \xi^*, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1 \xi^*, \tau) &= E_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2 \xi^*, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_1 \xi^*, \tau) &= Z_\phi(\zeta, \Gamma_2 \xi^*, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{16}$$

Since Γ_2 and Γ_1 are neutrosophic proximally commuting, we derive $\Gamma_1 \zeta = \Gamma_2 \zeta$. Again, by the condition $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq D_0(\tau)$, there exists an element $z \in C_0(\tau)$ such that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(z, \Gamma_1 \zeta, \tau) &= P_\phi(z, \Gamma_2 \zeta, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(z, \Gamma_1 \zeta, \tau) &= E_\phi(z, \Gamma_2 \zeta, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(z, \Gamma_1 \zeta, \tau) &= Z_\phi(z, \Gamma_2 \zeta, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{17}$$

Now, since Γ_1 proximally neutrosophic dominates Γ_2 , from 16 and 17, we get

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\zeta, z, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(\zeta, z, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\zeta, z, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(\zeta, z, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\zeta, z, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\zeta, z, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{18}$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$\left. \begin{aligned} 1 &\geq P_\phi(\zeta, z, \tau) \geq P_\phi\left(\zeta, z, \frac{\tau}{k}\right) \geq P_\phi\left(\zeta, z, \frac{\tau}{k^2}\right) \\ &\geq \dots \geq P_\phi\left(\zeta, z, \frac{\tau}{k^n}\right) \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \\ 0 &\leq E_\phi(\zeta, z, \tau) \leq E_\phi\left(\zeta, z, \frac{\tau}{k}\right) \leq E_\phi\left(\zeta, z, \frac{\tau}{k^2}\right) \\ &\leq \dots \leq E_\phi\left(\zeta, z, \frac{\tau}{k^n}\right) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \\ 0 &\leq Z_\phi(\zeta, z, \tau) \leq Z_\phi\left(\zeta, z, \frac{\tau}{k}\right) \leq Z_\phi\left(\zeta, z, \frac{\tau}{k^2}\right) \\ &\leq \dots \leq Z_\phi\left(\zeta, z, \frac{\tau}{k^n}\right) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{19}$$

Hence, by the definition of a neutrosophic metric space (NMS), we conclude $\zeta = z$. Thus, from 17, it follows that ζ is a common best proximity point for Γ_1 and Γ_2 .

Suppose that ζ^* is another common best proximity point of Γ_1 and Γ_2 such that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\zeta^*, \Gamma_1 \zeta^*, \tau) &= P_\phi(\zeta^*, \Gamma_2 \zeta^*, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(\zeta^*, \Gamma_1 \zeta^*, \tau) &= E_\phi(\zeta^*, \Gamma_2 \zeta^*, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(\zeta^*, \Gamma_1 \zeta^*, \tau) &= Z_\phi(\zeta^*, \Gamma_2 \zeta^*, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Now, since Γ_1 proximally neutrosophic dominates Γ_2 , and ζ and ζ^* are common best proximity points for Γ_1 and Γ_2 , we obtain

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\zeta, \zeta^*, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(\zeta, \zeta^*, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\zeta, \zeta^*, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(\zeta, \zeta^*, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\zeta, \zeta^*, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\zeta, \zeta^*, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (20)$$

Again, using the same reasoning as in (19), from (20), we deduce $\zeta = \zeta^*$. This completes the proof of the theorem. \square

Example 3.4. Consider $X = [0, 1]^2$ with metric $d((x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2)) = |x_1 - x_2| + |y_1 - y_2|$. Choose $C = \{(0, x) \mid 0 \leq x \leq 1\}$ and $D = \{(1, y) \mid 0 \leq y \leq 1\}$. Here, $C_0(\tau) = C$ and $D_0(\tau) = D$. Define $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 : C \rightarrow D$ as $\Gamma_1(x, y) = (1, \frac{y}{4})$ and $\Gamma_2(x, y) = (1, \frac{y}{32})$. Choose the CTN, $*$ as $a * b = ab$ and the CCTN \diamond as $a \diamond b = \max\{a, b\}$. The functions $P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi : \mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2 \times [0, \infty)$ are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(z_i, z_{i+1}, \tau) &= \frac{\tau}{\tau + d(z_i, z_{i+1})}, \\ E_\phi(z_i, z_{i+1}, \tau) &= \frac{d(z_i, z_{i+1})}{\tau + d(z_i, z_{i+1})}, \\ Z_\phi(z_i, z_{i+1}, \tau) &= \frac{d(z_i, z_{i+1})}{\tau}, \end{aligned}$$

where $z_i = (x_i, y_i)$ and $z_{i+1} = (x_{i+1}, y_{i+1})$, for $x_i, y_i, x_{i+1}, y_{i+1} \in \mathbb{R}$. And we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(C, D, \tau) &= \frac{\tau}{\tau + 1}, \\ E_\phi(C, D, \tau) &= \frac{1}{\tau + 1}, \\ Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) &= \frac{1}{\tau}, \quad \tau > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Claim I: Γ_1 proximally neutrosophic dominates Γ_2 .

Consider $(0, u_1), (0, u_2), (0, z_1), (0, z_2), (0, v_1), (0, v_2) \in C$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi((0, u_1), \Gamma_2(0, z_1), \tau) &= P_\phi((0, u_2), \Gamma_2(0, z_2), \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ P_\phi((0, v_1), \Gamma_1(0, z_1), \tau) &= P_\phi((0, v_2), \Gamma_1(0, z_2), \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi((0, u_1), \Gamma_2(0, z_1), \tau) &= E_\phi((0, u_2), \Gamma_2(0, z_2), \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi((0, v_1), \Gamma_1(0, z_1), \tau) &= E_\phi((0, v_2), \Gamma_1(0, z_2), \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi((0, u_1), \Gamma_2(0, z_1), \tau) &= Z_\phi((0, u_2), \Gamma_2(0, z_2), \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi((0, v_1), \Gamma_1(0, z_1), \tau) &= Z_\phi((0, v_2), \Gamma_1(0, z_2), \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Here, $u_i = \frac{z_i}{32}$ and $v_i = \frac{z_i}{4}$ for $0 \leq z_i \leq 1$, $i = 1, 2$.

Subclaim 1: $P_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) \geq P_\phi((0, v_1), (0, v_2), \tau)$, for some $k \in [0, 1)$.

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) &= \frac{k\tau}{k\tau + |u_1 - u_2|} \\ &= \frac{\tau}{\tau + \frac{|u_1 - u_2|}{k}} \\ &= \frac{\tau}{\tau + \frac{|\frac{z_1}{32} - \frac{z_2}{32}|}{k}} \\ &\geq \frac{\tau}{\tau + |\frac{z_1}{4} - \frac{z_2}{4}|}, \quad k \geq \frac{1}{8} \\ &= P_\phi((0, v_1), (0, v_2), \tau). \end{aligned}$$

The above inequality holds for $k \geq \frac{1}{8}$.

Subclaim 2: $E_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) \leq E_\phi((0, v_1), (0, v_2), \tau)$, for some $k \in [0, 1)$.

$$\begin{aligned} E_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) &= \frac{|u_1 - u_2|}{k\tau + |u_1 - u_2|} \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{k\tau}{|u_1 - u_2|}} \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{k\tau}{|\frac{z_1}{32} - \frac{z_2}{32}|}} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\tau}{|\frac{z_1}{4} - \frac{z_2}{4}|}}, \quad k \geq \frac{1}{8} \\ &= E_\phi((0, v_1), (0, v_2), \tau). \end{aligned}$$

The above inequality holds for $k \geq \frac{1}{8}$.

Subclaim 3: $Z_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) \leq Z_\phi((0, v_1), (0, v_2), \tau)$, for some $k \in [0, 1)$.

$$\begin{aligned} Z_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) &= \frac{|u_1 - u_2|}{k\tau} \\ &= \frac{|\frac{z_1}{32} - \frac{z_2}{32}|}{k\tau} \\ &\leq \frac{|\frac{z_1}{4} - \frac{z_2}{4}|}{\tau}, \quad k \geq \frac{1}{8} \\ &= Z_\phi((0, v_1), (0, v_2), \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Hence it holds for any $1 > k \geq \frac{1}{8}$.

Thus Γ_1 and Γ_2 satisfies the contraction condition.

Claim II: Γ_2 and Γ_1 neutrosophic proximally commute.

Let $w_1, w_2, z \in C$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(w_1, \Gamma_2 z, \tau) &= P_\phi(w_2, \Gamma_1 z, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(w_1, \Gamma_2 z, \tau) &= E_\phi(w_2, \Gamma_1 z, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(w_1, \Gamma_2 z, \tau) &= Z_\phi(w_2, \Gamma_1 z, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Then the only possible values of z, w_1 and w_2 are given by $z = (0, x)$, we have $w_1 = (0, \frac{x}{32})$ and $w_2 = (0, \frac{x}{4})$, for any $0 \leq x \leq 1$. Thus $\Gamma_1 w_1 = \Gamma_2 w_2 = (1, \frac{x}{128})$, for any $0 \leq x \leq 1$. Hence Γ_2 and Γ_1 neutrosophic proximally commute.

Clearly, $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq D_0(\tau)$ and $\Gamma_2(C_0(\tau)) \subseteq \Gamma_1(C_0(\tau))$ and the functions Γ_1 and Γ_2 are continuous. Thus, by Theorem 3.3, Γ the mappings Γ_1 and Γ_2 has a common best proximity point $(0, 0)$ in C .

4. Conclusions

Best proximity point theory is relevant in scenarios where fixed points do not exist. In particular, problems with the mappings defined between two non-overlapping sets where a fixed point is not possible. In order to solve this, best proximity point theory helps to find points in one set that are as close as feasible to their images in the other set. This idea is important to solve the problems where exact solutions are unattainable but best approximate solutions are meaningful and applicable.

Neutrosophic metric spaces are a generalized version of metric spaces and helps us to solve problems where information is vague or they consists of degrees of truth, falsity, and indeterminacy.

The two branches mentioned above are very relevant and has many applications. Hence, in this work, we coined the concepts of best proximity point theory and neutrosophic metric spaces. Thus, we extended the notion of common best proximity points for non-self mappings to the setting of neutrosophic complete metric spaces. Moreover, we proved results on the existence of common best proximity points for given contraction in the aforementioned space. Examples are given to support our results and our findings generalizes many known results in the literature.

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